

Review Chinese Exceptionalism by De-Essentialising China: Confucianism & Legalism

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This article critically examines Chinese exceptionalism by de-essentialising dominant narratives that overly emphasise Confucian pacifism while overlooking the influence of Legalism. Exceptionalism, as conceptualised by Nymalm and Plagemann (2019), reflects a paradox between universality and particularity, with Chinese exceptionalism projecting a narrative of moral superiority rooted in Confucian ideals. However, this narrative often disregards the pragmatic, amoral principles of Legalism, which historically shaped China's domestic and foreign policies. Through qualitative case studies of Confucianism and Legalism, this study deconstructs the myth of Chinese exceptionalism, revealing that China's historical approach to power reflects a blend of Confucian rhetoric and Legalist realism. While Confucianism promotes ideals of harmonious inclusion and benevolent governance, Legalism advocates for strict control, legal order, and power maximisation. By highlighting the duality between these two philosophical traditions, this work challenges the notion that China's rise will inherently follow a peaceful trajectory rooted in Confucian pacifism. Instead, it argues that contemporary Chinese foreign policy under Xi Jinping reflects a hybrid model, combining Confucian discourse with Legalist pragmatism. This deconstruction of Chinese exceptionalism provides policymakers and scholars with a more nuanced framework to assess China's foreign policy and its implications for global power dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

In International Relations (IR), great powers often invoke exceptionalism to differentiate themselves from others. Exceptionalism is a complex concept, intertwined with a state's history, culture, religion, philosophy, ethics, and more. Nymalm and Plagemann (2019, pp. 14-15) effectively conceptualise exceptionalism as a paradox between the universal and the specific. It involves the claim to a unique and exclusive understanding of the universal common good and the inclination to implement it beyond its historical context, articulated and enacted through foreign policy. The connection between a nation's foreign policies and its self-perception as a singular society or civilisation, often tied to a superior revelation or spiritual essence, underscores the idea of exceptionalism. This connection creates the exceptionalism paradox. On the one hand, it reflects exceptionalism's universality by claiming moral superiority over nearly all other societies, motivating the exceptionalist nation to pursue what it perceives as a universal common good in its foreign policy. On the other hand, it reflects exceptionalism's particularity by suggesting that other societies are incapable of replicating the unique attributes of the exceptional state. Nymalm and Plagemann (2019, pp. 18-19) categorise four types of exceptionalism in foreign policy: imperialist, civilisational, internationalist, and globalist exceptionalism. Notably, civilisational exceptionalism stands out as the predominant discourse, particularly with the rise of the concept of "civilisational state," as articulated by China, Turkey, India, Russia, and the United States (Acharya, 2020, p. 139). Civilisational exceptionalism is characterised by its model approach to foreign policy and its tendency to seek exceptions in international political matters. Although exceptionalism is not exclusively a phenomenon of great or superpowers, the level of power largely dictates the attention that discourses on exceptionalism receive (Nymalm and Plagemann, 2019, pp. 19-20).

This article explores the intricate discourse surrounding Chinese exceptionalism within the IR field. Undoubtedly, China has emerged as a major global power whose actions significantly influence IR and global power dynamics, as evidenced by the ongoing Sino-American competition. Understanding Chinese exceptionalism is crucial for explaining how China perceives its role and strategies on the world stage. Such insight also aids policymakers worldwide in developing informed and effective foreign policies and diplomatic strategies in response to China's actions and policies. This paper disentangles Chinese exceptionalism by highlighting the misinterpretation of Confucianism and the omission of Legalism in

mainstream discourse. By addressing these gaps, future academic discussions can approach Chinese exceptionalism from a new dimension, and policymakers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of China's foreign policy beyond the veil of Chinese exceptionalism.

This paper begins with a literature review that examines various perspectives on Chinese exceptionalism, covering both its historical roots and contemporary manifestations. This historical perspective provides a foundation for understanding the current expressions of Chinese exceptionalism in IR. The literature review also considers dissenting voices and critics of Chinese exceptionalism, identifying the gaps this article seeks to address. The second part of this work outlines the research methodology, which employs qualitative case studies. The third part is the central section that de-essentialises China through two case studies: Confucianism and Legalism. Although the discussion is primarily theoretical, a brief comparison is made between Chinese exceptionalism and China's foreign policy before the conclusion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The discourse surrounding Chinese exceptionalism is gaining prominence, driven by China's status as the foremost rising power and Beijing's efforts to address its soft power deficit (Zhang, 2011; Callahan, 2012; Wang, 2014). The current Chinese president, Xi Jinping, likely adheres to Chinese exceptionalism, given his inclination towards Chinese nationalism. He often appeals to China's illustrious culture and history to shape both China's domestic and foreign policies. In a 2014 speech, Xi stated, "The Chinese nation has always been peace-loving. Our love for peace is also deeply rooted in Confucianism. Since ancient times, Chinese people have esteemed ideas preaching peace: 'Coordinate and seek harmony with all nations,' 'Within the four seas, all men are brothers,' 'A far-off relative is not as helpful as a near neighbour,' 'Neighbours wish each other well, just as loved ones do to each other,' 'A warlike state, no matter how big, will inevitably die.' The love for peace has been firmly embedded in the spiritual world of the Chinese nation and remains China's basic stance in handling international relations." Similar sentiments are echoed in his other speeches and official Chinese documents, aligning with the emphasis on Chinese characteristics consistently highlighted by the Chinese Communist Party (CCP) (Xi, 2021; The State Council, 2011; The State Council, 2005).

As Zhang suggested, there are generally three waves of Chinese exceptionalism: imperial China (221 BC-AD 1911), the revolutionary People's Republic of China (PRC) (1949-1976), and post-1976 contemporary Chinese exceptionalism (Zhang, 2013, p. 308). It is impossible to comprehend contemporary Chinese exceptionalism without understanding its historical manifestations, as post-1911 Chinese exceptionalism draws heavily from the imperial legacy. The development of Chinese exceptionalism is primarily anchored on China's continuous civilisation, which spans thousands of years.

Zhang, however, overlooks Chinese exceptionalism during the republican era (1911-1949). Despite China's material backwardness at the time, nationalist leader Sun Yat-sen promoted the distinctiveness and moral superiority of Chinese civilisation compared to their Western counterparts (Acharya, 2020, p. 144; Sun, 1941). Given China's semi-colonial status during this period, that strand of Chinese exceptionalism attracted little attention, both then and afterwards. Furthermore, it reflected the Pan-Asianist discourse of the late 19th century and early 20th century, though this connection is often overlooked today due to Imperial Japan's use of Pan-Asianism to justify its imperialist ambitions (Duara, 2001).

This literature review focuses on Chinese exceptionalism in Imperial China (Ming and Qing Dynasties) and post-1978 (Reform and Opening Up) Chinese exceptionalism. The latter is crucial for understanding contemporary China's foreign policy and soft power, having the former as its most significant source of development. Mao's version of Chinese exceptionalism is unique compared to the other two strands. It blended traditional *tian xia* (All Under Heaven, 天下; this term is defined in the following paragraphs) aspirations with the modern ideology of communism (Chen, 2001; Xu, 2010). In fact, Mao Zedong denigrated Confucianism, believing that "political power grows out of the barrel of a gun" (Mao, 1974, p. 61). This revolutionary and offensive dimension of Mao's exceptionalism is unlikely to be revived and is thus only briefly mentioned here.

CHINESE EXCEPTIONALISM IN IMPERIAL CHINA

The concept of exceptionalism in Imperial China was embodied in the claims of its rulers and elite class regarding China's central and superior position in the world, along with assertions of a peace-loving Confucian foreign policy. Historically, Chinese exceptionalism arose from two significant factors: the early development of Chinese civilisation and the absence of rival civilisations nearby (Zhang, 2013, p. 308).

John Fairbank (1968, pp.1-2) writes, "Age, size, and wealth all made China the natural center of this East Asian world. Geography kept the whole region separate from West and South Asia and made it the most distinctive of all the great cultural areas." China's name, *Zhongguo* (中国), meaning "Middle Kingdom," *prima facie* indicates Imperial China's view of its centrality in the world (Zhang, 2013, p. 308).

The academic discussion of Chinese exceptionalism in Imperial China frequently references two intertwined concepts: the tributary system and *tianxia* (天下, All Under Heaven). The seminal literature from Fairbank (1942, 1953, 1968) provides valuable insights into the Imperial Chinese tributary system. To put it simply, the tributary system posited China as deserving of tribute from foreign leaders, who were, in turn, obligated to fulfil roles as subordinate or tributary states. According to David Kang (2010), the tributary system represented the international order in East Asia, with China at its centre. It was a hierarchical and stable system, especially from 1368 to 1841, as the idea of *Pax Sinica* suggests. *Tianxia* reflects China's assertion of Confucian moral authority over the known world, with Chinese emperors considering themselves as the "Son of Heaven" at the apex of the hierarchy (Zhang, 2013, p. 308). Thus, the tributary system was a materialisation of China's *tianxiaism*. Zhang (2013, p. 308) describes Sinocentrism as the "most noteworthy, consistent, and important dimension of the imperial discourse." It provides a rich reservoir for modern China to develop its exceptionalism.

CONTEMPORARY CHINESE EXCEPTIONALISM

Contemporary Chinese exceptionalism largely arises from Beijing's ambition to construct a strategic narrative and ideological rationale that supports a stable external environment for China's resurgence as a great power in today's global order. Zhang (2013, p. 310) argues that contemporary Chinese exceptionalism comprises three interconnected features derived from Imperial Chinese exceptionalism: great power reformism, benevolent pacifism, and harmonious inclusionism.

Indeed, both Chinese people and political elites harbour a great power dream derived from Imperial China's concept of the "heavenly dynasty" (天朝, *tianchao*) (Ren, 2009, p. 135). In an article by prominent Chinese IR scholar Yan Xuetong (2001, p. 33), he states, "The history of superpower status makes the Chinese people very proud of their country on the one hand, and on the other hand, very sad about China's current international status. They believe China's decline is a historical mistake they should correct." However, as a great power, China aims not to follow the historical trajectory of Western and Japanese powers, which conquered and colonised many other nations. Instead, a rising China strives to build a peaceful and harmonious world by sharing the benefits of its development with the world (Zhang, 2007; Zhang, 2013, p. 311). The best example is the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), comparable to Japanese official development assistance (ODA), through which many Eastern and Southeastern Asian countries improved their infrastructure (Söderberg, 2010, p. 37).

The concept of benevolent pacifism overlaps greatly with great power reformism. This idea is rooted in the historical narrative of Imperial China's peaceful and defensive foreign policy, shaped largely by Chinese culture. Consequently, the PRC is expected to rise peacefully, as peace is considered part of the "DNA" of Chinese culture (Zhang, 2013, pp. 311-312).

Harmonious inclusionism consists of a set of interconnected ideas that challenge the notion of a single nation, ideology, or methodology dominating global politics. Instead, it advocates for a receptive, open-minded approach to worldwide diverse political and cultural traditions. Through this concept, China seeks to enhance its engagement with the global community. Beyond merely recognising the importance of integrating various political and cultural traditions into international governance, "harmonious inclusionism" champions the involvement of all nations in pursuing collective security, growth, and well-being through open, reciprocal multilateralism and cooperation. This aims to achieve shared and universal prosperity for all countries, not just major powers.

China proposes extending the benefits of its growth to other nations, respecting political and cultural differences rather than imposing its political system on others, and working towards establishing a "harmonious world." This approach embodies the Confucian idea of "harmony in diversity" (和而不同, *he er bu tong*). In Confucian philosophy, "he" represents harmony (acknowledging differences while blending interactions), and "tong" signifies uniformity. Hence, the phrase suggests that the ideal person seeks harmony with others without necessarily adopting their views. Chinese intellectuals often argue that China's integrated approach to reasoning downplays individualism while fostering the peaceful coexistence of diverse elements, thereby showing tolerance towards other cultures and welcoming the

integration of various traditions into a cohesive process of reconciling differences (Zhang, 2013, pp. 311-312).

In the contemporary world, China's harmonious inclusionism challenges Western universalism by proposing alternative approaches. William Callahan (2004) argues that "harmony in diversity" reflects a flexible approach that uses diversity and uncertainty as tools to achieve the ideal state of "great harmony." This concept implies that nations should engage in peaceful interactions while maintaining their unique perspectives in international relations. This ensures that differences in opinion do not hinder amicable relations, positive engagements, or cooperative efforts beneficial to all involved (Ding, 2005, p. 29). However, Callahan (2016) holds reservations about the inclusiveness of Chinese foreign policy in practice, citing the deliberate exclusion of the US and Japan from the "inclusive" Belt and Road Initiative.

(2a) Civilisational State/Sino-Speak

The rise of Chinese exceptionalism coincides with the emergence of the Chinese civilisational state discourse, often referred to as "Sino-speak," a term coined by Callahan (2012, p. 33). This discourse justifies Chinese exceptionalism by portraying China as a civilisation completely different from, and perhaps superior to, the West.

Callahan (2012, p. 34) identifies Martin Jacques as a prime example of "Sino-speak" through his seminal work, *When China Rules the World: The End of the Western World and the Birth of a New Global Order*. However, he overlooks another critical contemporary Chinese scholar, Zhang Weiwei, the director of the China Institute at Fudan University, who authored the well-known book *The China Wave: Rise of a Civilizational State*. Indeed, other scholars might also be classified under "Sino-speak." For example, Lucian Pye (1992, p. 1162) views China as "a civilisation pretending to be a nation-state." In contrast to Zhang and Jacques, Pye's analysis is more introspective, focusing on how China's historical and cultural legacies influence the behaviour and attitudes of its leaders and citizens rather than starkly differentiating China from the West (Pye, 1990). Nevertheless, given Zhang and Jacques' active roles in academia and media, this paper focuses exclusively on their perspectives.

Martin Jacques introduces the concept of China as a "civilisational state," a term that sets China's socio-political identity apart from the typical nation-state model prevalent in the West. Jacques argues that the civilisational state views itself as uniquely grounded in its cultural mission, extensive history, vast territory, and Confucian philosophy. This contrasts with the Western notion of a nation-state, characterised by a relatively modern historical narrative, defined borders, and a homogenous national culture. Thus, the expectation for China to "Westernise" is deemed unrealistic. Jacques argues that, operating as a "civilisational state," China's politics, governance, and foreign relations fundamentally diverge from Western practices. He notes that the Chinese state's more paternalistic and meritocratic approach, rooted in Confucian ideals, informs its governance model focused on stability, order, and the collective good rather than individual freedoms. Jacques posits that China seeks not to export its model or ideology but to earn respect and influence through its distinctive status and historical legacy in international relations. He speculates that as China gains global prominence, its approach as a civilisational state may challenge the Westphalian international system, potentially reviving the tributary system (Jacques, 2009).

Zhang Weiwei characterises China as "the rise of a civilisational state which has amalgamated the world's largest continuous civilisation with a huge modern state" (Zhang, 2012, p. 47). He defines a civilisational state as a product of "hundreds of states amalgamated into one" throughout China's extensive and continuous history (Zhang, 2012, p. 53). His perspective shares some similarities with Martin Jacques', particularly in the belief that due to its unique history, China will not and should not align with Western norms in domestic politics and foreign policy. However, Zhang disagrees with Jacques on whether China will revive some form of the ancient tributary system. He contends that Jacques still sees an inherent tension between nation-state and civilisation-state models. Furthermore, while Zhang does not agree with Jacques on the notion of racial superiority, his discussion of the Chinese "civilisational state" nonetheless implies a certain superiority of Chinese civilisation (Zhang, 2012).

(2b) Chinese IR Theory

Since the 1990s, the scholarship of Chinese International Relations Theory (IRT) has emerged, led by three prominent scholars: Yan Xuetong, Zhao Tingyang, and Qin Yaqing. According to Do (2015, p. 24), the creation of the "Chinese School of IR" signifies a "generational change in Chinese social sciences,

particularly the professionalisation of its IR community and their aspiration to 'catch up' with the global intellectual community." These scholars criticise Western IR theories as "Eurocentric" in their interpretation of non-Western countries' foreign policies (Woon, 2018).

As the leading figure of the "Tsinghua School," Yan (2013) introduces moral realism in his book *Ancient Chinese Thought, Modern Chinese Power*, following a detailed examination of Pre-Qin (approximately 770 BC-221 BC) philosophy. 'Moral realism,' as articulated by Yan Xuetong, signifies a departure from traditional realist perspectives that emphasise power politics and strategic considerations, neglecting moral or ethical dimensions. He differentiates between hegemony or 'ba' (霸) and humane authority or 'wang' (王). The former relies on material power, exemplified by US hegemony, while the latter depends on moral leadership. Yan argues that moral leadership is more significant than economic and military power, deriving from the personal authority of a state's leader, the ministers they appoint, and the policies they pursue. Virtuous leadership from a leading power in international relations is likely to win global hearts and minds, contributing to a stable interstate system.

Zhao Tingyang (2006) is known for his *tianxia* theory in Chinese IR theories, which he elaborates on in *Rethinking Empire from a Chinese Concept 'All-Under-Heaven' (Tian-xia, 天下)*. All-under-heaven means an institutional world that is fundamentally different from conventional military empires such as the Roman Empire and imperial empires such as the British Empire (Tingyang, 2006, p. 30). Zhao defines the utopia of All-Under-Heaven as "an extendedly-defined world society with harmony, communication, and cooperation of all nations, guaranteed by a commonly-agreed institution" (Tingyang, 2006, p. 36). Zhao thinks Chinese political methodology is essentially different from the Western one (Tingyang, 2006, pp. 30-31). Chinese political thought conceptualises order through the prism of world/society, envisioning governance as an extension of harmonious relations on a global scale. In contrast, Western political thought is anchored in the paradigm of the nation/state, construing sovereignty as a self-contained entity defined by geographical, territorial, and juridical boundaries. Zhao (2006, p. 36) also compares the All-Under-Heaven pattern with the United Nations pattern and argues that the former is more successful, as demonstrated by the long periods of peace and stability in Chinese history. Zhao (2006, p. 37) believes that the different philosophies of the two patterns explain the consequential differences: All-Under-Heaven understands the oneness of the world as "harmony with differences," whereas the United Nations understands the oneness of the world as a mission of Western modernity. Therefore, the All-Under-Heaven theory is holistic and inclusive. Zhao suggests that it should be the best philosophy for world governance. Zhao (2021) further articulates his *tianxia* theory in his newest book, *All under Heaven: The Tianxia System for a Possible World Order*. He (2006, pp. 3-4) continues emphasising *tianxia* theory's inclusiveness and harmoniousness by comparing it with Western binary philosophy, for example, Christianity/paganism and Samuel Huntington's clash of civilisations.

Qin Yaqing (2016), another important scholar of the Chinese School of IR, developed relational theory. Qin sets Chinese relationality against Western rationality, basing his theory on Chinese dialectics. He (2016, p. 34) argues that individual rationality is "a defining element of the background knowledge of Western culture." Unlike the Hegelian 'thesis-antithesis' approach, which often involves conflict and synthesis in an "either-or" logic, Qin references Chinese *Zhongyong* (中庸) dialectics, symbolised by *yin* (阴) and *yang* (阳), to emphasise a non-conflictual, coevolutionary process ('co-theses'), which is "both-and" logic. *Zhongyong* dialectics lead to harmony by seeking a balanced middle ground for common interests. Yin and yang constitute an organic whole from which any other relationship can be seen as being derived (Yaqing, 2016, pp. 39-40). Qin (2016, p. 42) proposes that relational governance can be "an alternative and a complementary governing model to rule-based governance." Rule-based governance is designed to exploit the rationality of the individual actor, whereas relational governance is "a process of negotiating sociopolitical arrangements that manage complex relationships in a community to produce order so that members behave in a reciprocal and cooperative manner with mutual trust evolved over a shared understanding of social norms and human morality" (Yaqing, 2016, p. 43). In terms of IR, the mainstream IRT perceives an atomistic international system. By comparison, the relational approach understands it as a system of complex relations (Yaqing, 2016, p. 44).

However, Chinese IRT proponents do not necessarily endorse Chinese exceptionalism. They aim for their theories to be universal rather than national. Although they theorise on indigenous context, Chinese IRT does not self-exclude from Western IRTs (Li, 2021, p. 1399). For example, although Yan is often labelled a Chinese IRT scholar, his project aims to create a universal theory rooted in China's historical experience,

culture, and philosophy (Kim, 2016, p. 73). It must be noted that Chinese IRT largely develops based on Confucianism or the pacifist part of Confucianism. Zhao's *tianxia* theory and Qin's relational theory do implicitly suggest that their theories are perhaps better than Western ones that tend to produce disorder.

DISSENTING CHINESE NON-EXCEPTIONALISM

Nonetheless, the lure of Chinese exceptionalism is not appealing to every scholar in China and abroad.

(3a) Liu Mingfu

In China, Liu Mingfu, the author of *The China Dream: The Great Power Thinking and Strategic Positioning of China in the Post-American Age* and a retired Chinese PLA officer known for his hawkish views, believes that to safeguard its economic interests, China must enhance its military capabilities to counter American power (Liu, 2015). Otherwise, he argues, China would become a "plump lamb" vulnerable to other military powers (Liu, 2015, p. 255). For him, a nation cannot truly be a great power without the military strength to support its status.

Interestingly, despite his emphasis on military over civilian virtues, he does not see a Sino-US military conflict as inevitable. He argues that China's military strengthening is intended to deter a US attack. Moreover, his book reflects some Confucian influence, advocating that China, as a great power, should pursue the "kingly way" (王道, *wangdao*) rather than the "way of the hegemon" (霸道, *badao*) (Liu, 2015), a view also supported by Yan Xuetong (2013). This nuanced stance might explain why Callahan (2012, p. 34) still categorises Liu as part of "Sino-speak" because he highlights the Chinese version of modernisation as opposed to Western modernisation.

(3b) John Mearsheimer & John Ikenberry

In the West, leading neo-realist scholar John Mearsheimer (2014; 2021) is markedly more pessimistic than Liu and consistently challenges the notion of China's "peaceful rise." He posits that the international system is anarchic, lacking an overarching authority to regulate state actions. Within this framework, great powers inherently distrust each other and prepare for the worst-case scenario. Mearsheimer contends that as China's power grows, it will naturally aim to dominate Asia, much like the United States has sought dominance over the Western Hemisphere. This ambition for regional supremacy is likely to provoke tensions and potentially conflict with the US. He applies the concept of the security dilemma, in which one state's defensive measures are perceived as threats by others, resulting in an arms race and increased hostility. He argues that China's military strengthening, intended to secure its interests, will be viewed as aggressive by its neighbours and the US, escalating reciprocal suspicion and military buildup, thus rendering a peaceful rise highly improbable (Mearsheimer, 2014; 2021). Consequently, he gives minimal consideration to China's history and culture, viewing China as an unexceptional actor in the anarchic international system. Mearsheimer's argument appears plausible, as the Sino-US relationship has deteriorated significantly since 2016, with heightened tensions in the South China Sea and the Taiwan Strait.

In contrast, the liberal scholar John Ikenberry (2008) believed that a Sino-US power transition would unfold peacefully. He argued that the rise of China was not comparable to other precedents of great power rising because China was rising within the framework of a well-established liberal international system. China was already integrated into this system and benefiting from it. While the rise of China was unstoppable, Ikenberry believed that the US could fully integrate China into the liberal international order, and China would exercise its power within the framework of the international system. Thus, China would replace US hegemony but not the liberal order established by Washington. However, Ikenberry was overly optimistic about the permanence of the liberal order and underestimated China's ambitions to subvert it from within. Donald Trump's election cast significant doubt on the rules-based liberal order. China does not need to overturn the current international order but can substitute parts of it, such as with the establishment of the New Development Bank (NDB) and the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB). His later work also reflects the growing realisation of the challenges in fully integrating China into the rules-based liberal order (Ikenberry, 2017; Lim and Ikenberry, 2023).

CRITICS OF CHINESE EXCEPTIONALISM

The discourse of Chinese exceptionalism has undoubtedly faced criticism from several scholars. Callahan (2012, pp. 51-52) posits that "Sino-speak" is evolving into the predominant language to describe the convergence of a new form of Orientalism and the idea of Chinese exceptionalism. This 'Orientalism with Chinese characteristics' promotes Sinic values as the ethical antidote to what is depicted as a morally

declining and chaotic world, primarily influenced by US geopolitical interests (Zhang, 2013). By presenting ancient China as a benign regional hegemon and contemporary China as a continuation of Chinese civilisation, the People's Republic of China (PRC) is portrayed as naturally assuming the role of a responsible power. Woon (2018, p. 77) reflects on how Chinese exceptionalism grants discursive legitimacy to the notion of Sino-centric dominance in the 21st century, limiting the range of alternative visions for China's future. Ho (2014, p. 165) contends that both Chinese exceptionalism and non-exceptionalism, as viewed by John Mearsheimer, tend to essentialise China into an absolute identity, leaving no room for nuance. This binary perspective is counterproductive for comprehending China's aspirations for power within the international system.

More crucially, both contemporary and imperial forms of Chinese exceptionalism are often constructed through tactics such as selective interpretation of history and romanticising Chinese heritage. Callahan (2012, p. 37) criticises Martin Jacques because he “cherry-picks amenable facts from secondary sources for a simplistic and partisan reading of China's past and future.” Chinese history is far less peaceful than Chinese exceptionalism rhetoric suggests. The expansions of Chinese territories were not solely the result of cultural assimilation. Chinese territories significantly expanded during the Yuan and Qing dynasties, both referred to as alien/non-Han “conquest dynasties.” However, other Chinese dynasties, especially the Han and Tang, also tried to expand their territories (Zhang, 2015a, pp. 200-201). Even the Song Dynasty, often perceived as the weakest Chinese dynasty, did not refrain from expansion (Wang, 2011). These expansions were not merely defensive. For example, many early Ming campaigns in Mongolia/Yuan Dynasty were more offensive than defensive (Zhang, 2015b). Victoria Hui (2008, p. 58) said: “War, not Confucian ideals, explains how China expanded from the Yellow River valley in the Warring States era to the continental empire in the Qing dynasty.” Hans van de Ven (1996, p. 737) wrote: “Chinese history has been at least as violent as Europe's.”

Hui (2023) argues that many scholars view Imperial Chinese history from a Sino-centric perspective. This narrative can differ significantly when considering how neighbouring Confucianised states perceived Imperial China. Callahan (2012, p. 47) notes that Imperial Chinese sources often portray China as a benevolent empire. Kang (2010, p. 2) claims that China had no desire to expand because countries such as Vietnam and Korea voluntarily submitted to the China-centred tribute system and felt proud to be part of Confucian civilisation. John K. Fairbank (1942) introduced the tribute system by heavily relying on Chinese official sources. However, it is vital to consider the voices of those subjected to Imperial Chinese hegemony (Hui, 2023; Suzuki, 2009). Indeed, there is much evidence suggesting neighbouring countries had contradictory reactions. Zhang (2015b, p. 8) believes the tribute system was “constantly revised, challenged, or avoided by different actors.” Korea is commonly perceived as one of the Chinese tributary system's most “loyal” members. However, after researching Korean state letters, court documents, and personal essays, Lee (2017, p. 172) concluded that Korea's Ming policy “vacillated markedly from compliance (in 1370) to a failed challenge (in 1388), back to compliance (in 1392), and then to another attempt at challenge (in 1398).” In the early days of the Ming Dynasty, there were several diplomatic twists between Ming China and Choson Korea. Choson Korea officially adopted the ‘*sadae*’ (serving the great, 事大) policy after hearing of the Yongle emperor's “punitive expedition” against Vietnam to avoid a similar invasion (Zhang, 2015b, p. 76; Lee, 2017). Historically, Imperial China tried to invade Korea during the Han Dynasty, the Sui Dynasty, the Tang Dynasty, and the Mongolian Yuan Dynasty. Vietnam is another ‘loyal’ member of the Chinese tributary system. Imperial China ruled Vietnam for nearly one thousand years. Vietnam declared independence after the fall of the Tang Dynasty. Imperial China tried to reclaim Vietnam several times in the following centuries (Hui, 2023, pp. 487-488). The final peace between Imperial China, Vietnam, and Korea is more like the outcome of realist calculations in that China lacked the capacity to conquer and govern these territories while Korea and Vietnam, in turn, engaged in symbolic submission to China as the necessary price for stability. In fact, Vietnamese monarchs branded themselves “king” when communicating with China but “emperor” when in private or sending messages to their Southeast Asian “vassals” (Kang, 2010, p. 103).

Remaining Gaps

While many scholars have identified contradictions between Chinese exceptionalism and actual history, their critiques are somewhat superficial. They highlight the violent aspects of Imperial Chinese history; however, they have not sufficiently explained the rationale behind this contradiction. Hui (2023) de-essentialises China by examining other countries, but China itself is supposed to be de-essentialised first.

The rise of Chinese exceptionalism also represents China's response to Western centralism, although Beijing's counterattack has gone too far. Chinese culture has been essentialised in black-and-white terms. Many arguments from "Sino-speak" scholars are derived from this essentialised view of Chinese culture. Even prominent scholars like Henry Kissinger (2011, p. 5) believe in "the singularity of China." However, it makes no sense to claim that the culture of such an ancient and diverse civilisation is internally coherent and externally bound. Christian Reus-Smit (2018, p. 12) states, "the cultural terrain in which politics plays out is polyvalent, multilayered, riven with fissures, often contradictory, and far from coherently integrated or bounded." Peter Katzenstein (2009, p. 11) also warns against "coherent cultural complexes with dispositional essences." Similar critiques regarding the essentialism trap can also be observed from George Lawson (2012, p. 205) and Margaret Somers (1994, p. 605). Indeed, the so-called pacifist Confucianism must be re-examined, and Chinese culture should not be simplified as merely Confucianism.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a primarily qualitative research design. The qualitative research methodology was chosen for its efficacy in delving into complex phenomena within their unique contexts. Malterud (2001, p. 483) defines qualitative research methods as involving "the systematic collection, organisation, and interpretation of textual material derived from talk or conversation. It is used to explore the meanings of social phenomena experienced by individuals in their natural context." This approach is apt for studying Chinese exceptionalism, a topic rich with subtlety and complexity, facilitating a thorough comprehension of its principles, narratives, and ramifications.

The article utilises qualitative case studies of Confucianism and Legalism as a framework to de-essentialise Chinese exceptionalism. Confucianism is the first case because it is the most frequently discussed Chinese school of thought, and Chinese exceptionalism is largely based on Confucian pacifist culture. The second case is Legalism, another major Chinese school of thought, as important as Confucianism, but has received much less attention in the Anglophile world.

Qualitative case studies are designed to explore phenomena within their real-life contexts, incorporating a variety of data sources. This approach ensures that the subject is viewed from multiple perspectives rather than through a singular lens, facilitating a thorough understanding of the phenomenon's different facets (Baxter and Jack, 2008). Yin (2003) suggests that a case study approach is particularly useful in scenarios where: (1) the study seeks to answer "how" and "why" questions; (2) the behaviour of participants cannot be manipulated by the researcher; (3) there is a focus on examining contextual factors believed to be relevant to the phenomenon under study; or (4) the boundaries between the phenomenon itself and its context are not clear.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate how Confucianism and Legalism can be employed to de-essentialise China. The outcome is not predetermined. Confucianism and Legalism were two major schools of thought in ancient China, so they are highly relevant to debunking Chinese exceptionalism. The phenomenon of Chinese exceptionalism is still developing. These two case studies are characterised as exploratory, as they seek to investigate the phenomenon of Chinese exceptionalism, which does not have a predetermined set of outcomes (Yin, 2003), and intrinsic, given their unique relevance to the study of this particular phenomenon (Stake, 1995).

The paper primarily relies on secondary sources for these case studies, supplemented by textual analysis to support the arguments. In the first case study, the work here reviews the mainstream and alternative views on Confucianism through secondary source analysis, supported by some textual analysis from Confucius and Mencius. In the second case study, the work reviews relevant secondary sources about Legalism to find out how Legalism is different from but connected to Confucianism. The analysis will also be supported by some textual analysis from prominent Legalists—Hanfeizi and Shang Yang.

CASE I: CONFUCIANISM

The Myth of Confucian Pacifism

It is often taken for granted that Confucianism equates to pacifism. The myth of Confucian pacifism suggests that Confucian principles dictated Imperial China's defensive foreign policy. The long history of *Pax Sinica* that continued till the second half of the 19th century provides the most powerful justification (Zhang, 2015a, p. 200). Even several leading scholars in the West subscribe to the view that Confucian culture dictates China's peace-loving tradition. Since the Enlightenment, philosophers have touted

Chinese civilisation as “rational and peaceful” (Waldron, 1997, p. 36). Max Weber (1951, p. 140) wrote, “The Confucianists, who are ultimately pacifist literati oriented to inner political welfare, naturally faced military powers with aversion or lack of understanding.” John K. Fairbank (1974, pp. 7-9) contended that Chinese culture’s “pacifist bias” renders the use of force a “last resort.” Ralph Sawyer (1996, p. 3) argued, “Despite incessant barbarian incursions and major military threats throughout their history...Imperial China was little inclined to pursue military solutions to external aggression.” However, Confucianism is more complex and nuanced than what these scholars believe.

The narrative of Confucian pacifism is essentially a philosophical ideal that can never come into effect in the real world. A perfect pacifist world is only possible in the ideal of *tian xia*, a harmonious but hierarchical political order without state borders, where a sage King at the apex governs by utilising virtue. In this ideal circumstance, the use of force can find no justification. Confucius and Mencius also acknowledged the difficulty or impossibility of implementing their *tian xia* governed by a sage king through benevolence (Bell, 2008, pp. 227-229). Even Yao and Shun, the icons of sagehood, are not considered qualified sage kings:

Zigong said: What would you say of a man who showers the people with blessings and who could save the multitude? Could he be called benevolent? The Master said: What has this to do with goodness? He would be a saint! Even Yao and Shun would be deficient in this respect (Confucius et al., 2014, p. 17).

The closest real-world example to Confucian *tian xia* is the Imperial Chinese tributary system, although the latter resembles the former primarily in theory rather than practice.

The discussion below is based on classical Confucianism instead of neo-Confucianism. Neo-Confucianism, which was developed in the Song Dynasty (960 AD-1279 AD), became the state ideology during the Ming (1368 AD-1644 AD) and Qing (1644 AD-1911 AD) eras. Ming neo-Confucianism also stresses a hierarchical *tian xia* order, where the Chinese emperor, as the ultimate authority, governs by self-cultivation. In turn, subordinates show their appreciation for the emperor through loyalty and obedience. Punitive expeditions are responses to serious crimes, such as threatening Chinese security or executing Chinese envoys, and serve to express the emperor’s awesomeness (Zhang, 2015a, pp. 203-204). The development of neo-Confucianism also mirrors the growth and maturity of the Chinese tributary system. However, it is the classical version that significantly shaped Imperial Confucianism overall (Hui, 2018, p. 156).

Missionary Confucianism: Just War/Punitive Expedition

Confucianism does not rule out the possibility of deploying force, and several scholars have highlighted the Confucian endorsement of violence under plausible circumstances (Bell, 2008; Twiss and Chan, 2015; Yan, 2013). Confucius and Mencius were not blind to the semi-anarchic Chinese Warring States period in which they lived. Bell (2008, p. 230) thinks that most of the passages in *The Analects of Confucius* and *The Works of Mencius* are written in the context of a non-ideal world of states competing for territorial advantage, and they justify the use of force in a realistic world.

Mencius posits that small states should bolster their defences when threatened by larger states, advocating for the reinforcement of territorial boundaries: “Dig deeper moats and build higher walls and defend them together with the people” (Mengzi et al., 2009, p. 24). A defensive war is justified if a virtuous ruler must deploy violence with his people’s support to protect his territory from being conquered by other states (Bell, 2008, p. 231).

The most critical perspective from Confucius and Mencius involves the concept of just war or punitive expeditions. A war is considered just if it promotes peace and benevolence. To launch a just war, one must meet specific requirements. Bell (2008, pp. 235-237) summarises four requirements: “First, the ‘conquerors’ must try to liberate people who are being oppressed by tyrants... Second, the people must demonstrate, in concrete ways, that they welcome their conquerors... Third, punitive expeditions must be launched by rulers who are at least potentially virtuous... Fourth, the leader of justified punitive expeditions must have some moral claim to have the world’s support.” The Confucian justification of “punitive expeditions” seems to resemble the justification of humanitarian intervention from Michael Walzer (1977, p. 101). Bell (2008, p. 242) even believes Confucians might be more supportive of “punitive expeditions” launched against Iraq and Afghanistan compared to Western liberal defenders of humanitarian intervention. Kim (2010, p. 33; 2017, p. 193) describes a “punitive expedition” as “Confucian

moralpolitik” and “an intervention by a humane foreign ruler.” Kim (2017, pp. 191-192) stresses that a “punitive expedition” is impossible without a moral hierarchy among the states. Kim also notes that the primary purpose of the punitive expedition, according to Mencius, is to punish the unvirtuous ruler rather than save the people (Kim, 2017, p. 197). However, the people’s living conditions indicate whether the ruler is a sage king or a tyrant. This is different from modern humanitarian intervention, which aims “to protect the citizens of the target state from flagrant violations of their fundamental human rights usually by agents of the state” (Ayoob, 2002, p. 81). A good case study is Qi’s punitive expedition against Yan:

Now, Yan oppressed its people, and you went and punished its ruler. The people believed you were going to deliver them from out of the flood and fire and, bringing baskets of rice and pitchers of drink, they welcomed your army. Then you slew their fathers and older brothers, bound their sons and younger brothers, destroyed their ancestral temple, and carried off their treasured vessels-how can this be condoned? Certainly the world fears the might of Qi. Now you have doubled your territory but have not practiced humane government; it is this that is setting the troops of the realm in motion. If you will immediately issue orders to return the captives and halt the removal of the treasured vessels, and if you consult with the people of Yan about withdrawing once a ruler has been installed for them, you may still be able to stop an attack (Mengzi et al., 2009, pp. 23-24).

Qi’s punitive expedition meets the first requirement. It also met the second requirement initially but failed shortly after. Qi’s tyrannical actions in Yan made Qi’s ruler wicked and caused him to lose the world’s support. In this case, Mencius saw Yan’s illegitimate royal transmission between Zikuai and Zihui as the primary justification for a “punitive expedition” because it was not sanctioned by the Mandate of Heaven, rather than the suffering of the people (Mengzi et al., 2009, pp. 43-44).

Confucianism possesses a missionary aspect. A virtuous ruler is expected to extend benevolence beyond their borders, as it is theoretically possible for everyone to be “civilised” (Confucius et al., 2014, pp. 24-25 and 46). Confucius and Mencius allow for legal punishments when other means of promoting benevolence and preventing immoral behaviour prove ineffective (Confucius et al., 2014, p. 35; Mengzi et al., 2000, pp. 138-139). In the West, the binary is the “civilised” West vs. the “barbarian” non-West. In China, the binary is the “civilised” Middle Kingdom vs. the “barbarian” nomads. Phillips (2021, pp. 119, 190, 192) employs the terms “Confucian man’s burden,” “Confucian ‘civilising mission,’” and “Confucian assimilation” to highlight the hypocrisy. However, the Confucian missionary spirit is not comparable to Western Christianity, as Imperial China did not send missionaries to promote Confucianism, and the Confucian cultural bloc is limited to East Asia and Vietnam. Western civilisation spread far beyond Europe.

Nevertheless, it must be emphasised that war can only be launched to spread peace and benevolence. A war is unjust if it is launched for purposes other than rectifying aggression and tyranny (Bell, 2008; Twiss and Chan, 2015). Therefore, a war launched to enlarge territory and weaken other states is unjust:

Mencius said, “Those who serve the ruler today will say, ‘We can enlarge the lord’s territory and expand his treasuries and storehouses.’ And, in the present age, for this they are called ‘good ministers,’ whereas in antiquity they would have been called ‘thieves of the people.’ To seek the enrichment of a ruler who neither follows the Way nor commits himself to humaneness is to enrich a Jie. Those who say, ‘We can form alliances with other states so that his military campaigns will be successful’ are, in the present age, called ‘good ministers.’ Whereas in antiquity they would have been called ‘thieves of the people.’ To bolster the military strength of a ruler who neither follows the Way nor commits himself to humaneness is to support a Jie. Even if he were to receive all-under-Heaven as a gift, one who follows the way of the present day without having changed present practices would be unable to dwell in it for the space of a single morning (Mengzi et al., 2009, p. 140).

Lastly, Bell’s interpretation of Confucian just war requirements has faced criticism. An independent scholar, Hagen Kurtis (2022), argues that Bell’s interpretation is overly lenient. Launching a “punitive expedition” is acting as an agent of Heaven (“a minister appointed by Heaven”), and the requirements of “being potentially virtuous” and “having some moral claims of the world’s support” are too weak to be standard (Mengzi et al., 2009, p. 44). Kurtis points out that Confucian requirements for a just war are so

strict that they can hardly be met in the real world. That is why Confucianism is almost equivalent to pacifism. Additionally, Sungmoon Kim (2017, pp. 196-197) believes that even large-scale human rights violations and local people's wholehearted support are insufficient for intervention. Nonetheless, it is also odd to argue that Confucius and Mencius were merely thinking in the context of a utopian world without linking to the realist Chinese Warring States era.

That said, how we interpret Confucian just war theory is of secondary importance when integrating Chinese exceptionalism with international relations (IR), as the following discussion will illustrate. This paper favours Bell's approach, as it aligns more closely with the practical application of Confucian just war theory.

The Risk of Manipulation In IR

It seems that peace is embedded in Confucianism, and the requirements for punitive expeditions can constrain China from launching any expansionist campaigns. However, Confucian requirements for launching a just war are vague and subject to practical manipulation:

Mencius said, "A hegemon uses force under the pretext of benevolence," "a true king uses virtue and benevolence," "The Spring and Autumn Annals acknowledged no just wars. There are only cases of some wars not being as bad as others. A punitive expedition refers to a higher authority attacking a lower one. Peers should not launch punitive expeditions against one another." It is pronounced. One can say that the First Gulf War is a just war authorised by the United Nations, similar to "a guilty duke corrected [punished] by the Son of Heaven." It is like a conflict with a "higher authority attacking a lower one." In this war [the 2003 invasion of Iraq], the United States says it is using force to exercise benevolence, that it is acting as both a true king and a hegemon. However, the Second Gulf War is not the same, because without the authorisation of the United Nations, the United States and the United Kingdom are attacking an enemy state with vastly different [inferior] power and resources. In this war, the United States is using force under the pretext of benevolence, and it is also maintaining its geopolitical, national security, and economic interests in the name of promoting democracy in the Middle East; it is obviously acting as a global hegemon (Gong Gang, 2003, as cited by Bell, 2008, pp. 238-239).

No objective metrics are used to evaluate whether a country obeys the Confucian requirements for launching a "punitive expedition," unlike Western "universal values," which can at least refer to the UN Declaration of Human Rights. Still, this does not always prevent Washington from launching wars in the name of spreading democracy and human rights to legitimise its actions. In the future, Beijing could do the same in the name of promoting global peace and harmony, considering some historical precedents. Imperial China invaded Vietnam in the early fifteenth century in the name of a "punitive expedition." Chinese territory greatly expanded during the reign of Emperor Wu of the Han Dynasty. Hui (2018, p. 156) characterises Emperor Wu's foreign policy as "militarism with a Confucian façade." Confucianism was elevated as the official ideology during the Han Dynasty; however, since then, "warfare was considered to be a special application of justified punishment of...those who refused to acknowledge the authority of the legitimate emperor" (Yates, 2009, p. 25). The Han Dynasty defined the Xiongnu as the "enemy of virtue and humanity," and it was the duty of the virtuous emperor to "punish" them (Zhu and Wang, 2008, p. 273).

Given its resources, a hegemon can easily manipulate circumstances to fulfil most requirements for launching a "punitive expedition." The US has been very successful in portraying itself as the "defender of the free world" or the "Kingly Way" and in demonising its rivals through misinformation, even fabricating atrocities (Abrams, 2023). Indeed, a hegemon is often the most powerful in both hard and soft power (Nye, 1990). Due to its absolute advantage in military, technology, and economy, challenging the US is burdensome, making it feasible to gain "world support" to launch a "punitive expedition." It is difficult to predict if people from the "repressive regimes" would welcome the "liberators." However, it does not matter, as a hegemon or a (manipulated) true king would be unlikely to withdraw the troops once the "punitive expedition" commences with (manipulated) moral legitimacy and world support. Several other scholars share this view (Yan and Huang, 2011; Johnston, 2020). Yan and Huang (2013, p. 140) write, "Hegemony can of itself generate legitimacy for the use of military force." Johnston (2020, p. 68)

even thinks “moral realpolitik” effectively makes war easier to launch, observing that the rhetoric of just war “shifts the responsibility for warlike behaviour onto the enemy.”

Moreover, the Mencian-Confucian discourse justifies China and other Confucian countries in launching a “punitive expedition,” but other countries may find the Mencian-Confucian discourse incongruent with their values (Kim, 2017, p. 200). Today, Washington accuses Beijing of being a non-democratic regime even though the latter never endorses the Western notion of liberal democracy, which is similar to the missionary aspect of Confucianism.

In conclusion, while Confucianism contains significant pacifist elements, there is no consensus on how to interpret its standards for launching a punitive expedition or just war. Given its potentially coercive nature, it is inadequate to essentialise Confucianism as pacifist. Confucian pacifism, as many scholars understand, exists neither in theory nor in practice. Similar to the romanticisation of Chinese history, Confucianism is often cherry-picked to suit the PRC’s foreign policy strategy for creating a peaceful environment for its rise. This does not mean that the PRC will continue to rise peacefully and be a peace-loving hegemon, as advocated by Chinese exceptionalism. It is neither sensible nor feasible to dismiss the possibility that the PRC may exhibit missionary or paternalistic tendencies, particularly in light of Beijing’s increasingly assertive and at times coercive foreign policy, manifested most evidently in the South China Sea and vis-à-vis Taiwan. To suggest that the PRC will be a benevolent hegemon due to certain Confucian pacifist elements in its philosophical tradition is as disingenuous as insisting that the US is a peace-loving country on account of its liberal democratic institutions that constrain recourse to war, as per the democratic peace theory (Rosato, 2003).

CASE II: LEGALISM

If the case study of Confucianism is not strong enough to rebut Chinese exceptionalism due to its contentious punitive expedition/just war concept, Legalism can serve as a more tenable case study.

By comparison, Legalism has received almost no attention in the discussion surrounding Chinese exceptionalism. Among the debates regarding Chinese history, culture, and philosophy, the most frequently mentioned school of thought is Confucianism. Confucianism has always been the one that Beijing references to showcase China’s peace-oriented culture. This makes sense, given that Confucianism was elevated to the state ideology by Emperor Wu in the Han Dynasty, and subsequent dynasties upheld Confucianism’s orthodox position. This historical incident generated the misperception that China’s tradition was predominantly Confucian (Hui, 2008). The perception that Confucianism is the sociocultural doctrine shaping Chinese society is largely accurate at the ontological and epistemological levels. However, it is not necessarily true in the sense of sociopolitical norms (Zha, 2022, p. 335). Apart from Confucianism, there are many other “Hundred Schools of Thought,” such as Daoism, which played an influential role in shaping post-Han China and competed with Confucianism (Zhang, 2015a, p. 199).

This work contends that integrating Legalism into the debate is the most potent argument for debunking the myths of Chinese exceptionalism. The influence of Legalism on China is arguably at least as crucial as that of Confucianism. Though Emperor Wu of Han upheld Confucianism as the official ideology, Hsiao Kung-chuan (1976, p. 137) called his policy “Legalism with a Confucian façade.” Zhang (2015a, p. 216) writes, “Contemporary Chinese foreign policy may be influenced by various schools of ancient Chinese thought, Confucianism being just one of them. Indeed, if China’s historical experience is any guide, a quite possible outcome is that of a blend of Confucianism and Legalism to guide policy, as has repeatedly been the case in the long history of Chinese politics and foreign policy. For some intriguing reasons that historians are still debating, a Confucian-Legalist liaison has proved to be the most consequential—almost a norm—throughout Chinese history.” Zha (2022, p. 335) thinks that, more precisely speaking, the Chinese sociocultural doctrine is characterised as “Confucianism in semblance and Legalism in essence” (*ru biao fa li*, 儒表法里). However, Legalism has not received enough attention in the Chinese exceptionalism debate.

Realism With Chinese Characteristics

Legalism is one of the pre-Qin “Hundred Schools of Thought,” encompassing a collection of principles regarding statecraft that provide strategies for rulers to efficiently manage and control their governments, maximise state wealth, and expand territorial boundaries. In contrast with Confucianism, Legalism views human beings as inherently selfish, and education or self-cultivation cannot overcome this. Legalist thinking is premised on how people actually behave rather than on Confucian optimistic beliefs about

how people ought to behave. They believe people are inherently self-interested and require external discipline to meet the state's needs. It makes sense that Legalists advocate for a robust and central state that maintains control through rigid enforcement of laws and functions through a merit-based bureaucracy. The Legalist approach is pragmatic and amoral. The primary goal of the state is to enhance its power. Moral justification is utterly unconcerned with the institutions and methods Legalists advocate. This often justifies harsh penalties and rigid controls over society to secure compliance and deter dissent (Zha, 2022; Pines, 2014; Fraser, 2011). A passage from *The Lord of Shang*, a seminal Legalist book by Shang Yang, well explains this realism with Chinese characteristics:

Among the people's external tasks, nothing is more difficult than war; hence, he who takes law lightly cannot cause them [to engage in] it. What is called "taking law lightly"? It means that rewards are few, awe is meager, and excessive ways are not blocked. What are called "excessive ways"? It means that the argumentative and clever are esteemed, itinerant servants are employed, men of letters and those who have privately established a name are deemed illustrious. When these three are not blocked, the people do not engage in war, and undertakings end in defeat. Thus, when rewards are few, those who heed [others] do not benefit; when awe is meager, those who violate [orders] are not harmed. Hence, to attract [subjects] by opening excessive ways and to let them wage war while taking law lightly are like making a cat bait for a rat: Is it not too much?

Hence, he who wants to enable his people to wage war must take laws seriously. His rewards must be abundant, [his] awe must be severe; excessive ways must be blocked: the argumentative and clever should not be esteemed, itinerant servants should not be employed, men of letters and those who have privately established a name should not be illustrious. When rewards are abundant and awe is severe, the people see that he who [excels] at war is abundantly rewarded, and they forget about death; they see that those who do not fight are degraded and then regard life with bitterness. When rewards cause them to forget about death, while awe causes them to regard life with bitterness, and, moreover, excessive ways are blocked: to face the enemy in this situation is like shooting at a floating leaf with a hundred-*shi*-capacity crossbow- How can it not be pierced through? (Shang and Pines, 2017, pp. 228-229).

Regarding foreign policy and interstate relations, Legalists hold beliefs opposite to those of Confucianists. Legalists contend that the state should practice hegemony (*ba* 霸) as opposed to humane authority (*wang* 王). They are material determinists, believing that the cause of interstate war is the selfishness of human nature (Yan, 2013, pp. 28-29, 33). Hanfeizi, a prominent Legalist, attributes the origin of conflict to the failure of material goods to meet demand: "Hence the number of people increases, goods grow scarce, and men have to struggle and slave for a meager living. Therefore, they fall to quarrelling, and though rewards are doubled, and punishments are piled on, they cannot be prevented from growing disorderly" (Han, 2003, Section 49, *The Five Vermin*). He is frank about the cruel interstate competition and perceives force as the most effective way to achieve peace: "It is customary with a ruler that, if his state is small, he will do the bidding of larger states, and if his army is weak, he will stand in fear of stronger armies. When the larger states come with demands, the small state must consent; when strong armies appear, the weak army must submit" (Han, 2003, Section 9, *The Eight Villainies*). He maintains that being a hegemon is the best guarantee of security in the international system (Yan, 2013, p. 47). Hanfeizi does not think there are any substantial differences between hegemony and humane authority because, as he understands it, humane authority also depends on military might and a legal system rather than on morality, given changing times. Hanfeizi does not unconditionally reject the role of morality in foreign policy. Morality can play a role under two conditions: the main threat is from animals and illness, and human beings do not need to worry about basic needs such as clothing and food (Han, 2003, Section 49, *The Five Vermin*).

Legalism is rudimentarily similar to realism but presents methodological distinctions. Some scholars draw comparisons between Legalism and Machiavellian realism, noting that Legalism is more "scientific" in its approach. Unlike Machiavellian realism, which emphasises the personal qualities and cunning of individual rulers, Legalism focuses primarily on the institutions designed to control officials and the populace, which are the sources of the state's wealth and military power (Fraser, 2011). It is comparable to Morgenthau's view that politics should be governed by objective laws rooted in human nature and that law is an instrument to exercise power (Morgenthau and Thompson, 1985).

Confucian Façade and Legalism Core

Historically, Legalism and Confucianism managed to coexist. Qin was the first state to practice Legalism, and it ended up being the victor of the Warring States period by unifying China. However, the Qin Dynasty (221 BC-207 BC) did not last more than two decades, largely due to its harsh Legalist policies. Confucianism gained popularity in the following Han Dynasty, but Legalism did not disappear from history. The two opposing schools of thought formed a *de facto* marriage. The Confucian-Legalist sociopolitical system gradually merged ideological and political factors and continued to serve the Chinese state. Confucianism continues to cultivate people through normative values, while Legalism shapes the state's sociopolitical actions given its pragmatism. Therefore, the monologue of Confucianism as the official ideology, as highlighted by Imperial China and the PRC, is more rhetorical than real (Zhao, 2015; Yang, 2020; Zha, 2022).

To better explain the dynamics between Confucianism and Legalism, this paper lists some examples from Imperial China showing how Confucianism supplements structural realism. The Ming Dynasty reached its nadir in the mid-16th century. Structural realists thought that the Ming should accommodate the Mongols by accepting the Mongol request for trade and tribute. However, the Ming quickly reversed the accommodation policy after facing opposition from Confucian officials, as compromising with the enemies, "barbarians" such as the Mongols in particular, would damage China's prestige. During the Song Dynasty, Song and Xi Xia faced the threat from the Liao Empire. Realistically speaking, Song should have allied with Xi Xia if the balance of power logic were applied. However, an alliance with Xi Xia was virtually impossible because Song treated Xi Xia, a state governed by "barbarians," as a vassal state. Another example is the tribute system. The Chinese empire did not expand as the Western powers did. Instead, Imperial China's influence spread through the unique tribute system. The Ming Dynasty chose to establish the tribute system rather than conquering the states that Zheng He's naval fleets visited (Wang, 2015, pp. 186-187). However, as discussed in the literature review, this tributary system inevitably had a coercive element, as neighbours such as Vietnam and Korea had to join the system to symbolically acknowledge their vassal positions vis-à-vis China. Hence, superficially, the tributary system was Confucian, but its emergence was not completely based on the voluntary consent of its members.

To conclude the case study of Legalism, this section introduces Legalism and its influence in China. Legalism presents a powerful argument against the official narrative of Chinese exceptionalism. From the PRC's perspective, the essential purpose of constructing the Chinese exceptionalism narrative is to frame Imperial China as a benevolent hegemon; consequently, the PRC will also be a benevolent hegemon because it is the inheritor of a thousand-year-old peaceful Chinese civilisation. However, the concept of Legalism or the "Confucian façade and Legalism core," with its marked similarity to Western realism, can potentially deliver a death blow to most of the myths hidden under the narrative of Chinese exceptionalism. This also explains why the PRC never promotes Legalism in its soft-power campaign.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

After evaluating Chinese exceptionalism in theory, this work aims to briefly test Chinese exceptionalism in practice by investigating the extent to which Chinese foreign policy reflects its exceptional narrative. Exceptionalism does not dictate policy, but it reflects the political elite's worldview and can influence policy ideas (Zhang, 2013, p. 307).

The official rhetoric of Chinese foreign policy is largely consistent with the pacifist part of Confucianism. In the early days of the PRC, Premier Zhou Enlai enunciated the "Five Principles of Peaceful Coexistence" in 1954: mutual respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity, mutual non-aggression, non-interference in internal affairs, equality and mutual benefit, and peaceful coexistence (Nathan and Zhang, 2022, p. 59). After the Cold War, President Jiang Zemin articulated the "new security concept," which means "rise above one-sided security and seek common security through mutually beneficial cooperation" (Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2002). Then, in the early 2000s, President Hu Jintao introduced "peaceful rise" or "peaceful development" (The State Council, 2005). Current President Xi Jinping has taken a fundamental shift in foreign policy style by adopting a more proactive approach in the international system. Still, he has emphasised China's insistence on peaceful rise by introducing the "Community of Shared Future" (Xi, 2017). This concept essentially suggests that China will share its development with others. However, Xi's version of peaceful rise has some preconditions, according to Jian Zhang (2015c). The first is the unprecedented emphasis on the protection of China's national interests, which may prevail over a peaceful rise (Zhang, 2015, p. 9). Xi (2013) stressed that "we must adhere to the path of peaceful development, but we must never give up our legitimate rights and interests, and we must never sacrifice our national core

interests. No sovereign country should expect us to trade our core interests, and do not expect us to swallow the bitter fruit of undermining our sovereignty, security, and development interests.” China’s almost unconditional stance on “core interests” explains why China has been assertive on issues in the East China Sea, South China Sea, and Taiwan. Another important precondition of Xi’s version of peaceful rise is reciprocity (Zhang, 2015, p. 10). Xi (2013) stated that “China is on the path of peaceful development, and other countries must also follow the path of peaceful development. Only when all countries follow the path of peaceful development can they develop together and live in peace with each other.” This means China reserves the right to react or defend itself if any country tries to contain China or even wage war against it. It appears that the non-Confucian part of Chinese foreign policy is becoming evident since the Xi administration.

In practice, Chinese foreign policy is more complicated. China has a particular focus on its neighbours and deploys “peripheral diplomacy” regarding them. “Peaceful Rise” and the “Community of Shared Future” or “Community of Common Destiny” (人类命运共同体 *ren lei ming yun gong tong ti*) mainly target China’s neighbours, as China’s rise can only take place in a stable environment (Zhang, 2015c, p. 11). However, as the term “peripheral diplomacy” indicates, China has a top-down paternalistic attitude toward its neighbours. From the 1950s to post-2009 Chinese foreign policy, Beijing has been consistent with its Legalist “carrots and sticks” style foreign policy towards its neighbours. China rewards them when they are cooperative in preventing a rival great power (the US) from gaining influence at China’s expense and punishes them when they do the opposite (Li, 2016, p. 251). In 2010, Chinese foreign minister Yang Jiechi spoke to ASEAN, saying, “China is a big country, and you are small countries, and that is a fact” (cited by Cronin & Neuhard, 2020). China has territorial disputes with several ASEAN countries. Although China officially opens to dialogue, it has increased control over claimed territory in the South China Sea and even delegitimises unfavourable rules of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (Cronin & Neuhard, 2020, p. 14). The idea of a “community of shared future” is largely employed to mend fences with those ASEAN countries (Zhang, 2015c, p. 15).

President Xi Jinping’s mindset resembles that of a Legalist. Although he frequently references Confucian classics, Xi is a strong advocate of Legalist governance in terms of domestic politics. Early in his tenure, he began emphasising the phrase “govern the state according to law” (依法治国 *yi fa zhi guo*). He aimed to discipline the CCP through top-down law, launching an unprecedented anti-corruption campaign within the CCP. The rationale behind these policies is rooted in Legalist methods that emphasise controlling human behaviour through rewards and punishments administered by the state. Xi’s foreign policy also resonates with the Legalist worldview of interstate competition. Essentially, Xi’s ambition is to fulfil the “Chinese Dream” of the “rejuvenation of the Chinese nation” so that China will not be vulnerable to foreign threats, as it was during the “Century of Humiliation” (Schneider, 2016). On one hand, he prioritises Chinese core interests; on the other, he advocates for “win-win” solutions. He is likely trying to find a balance that allows him to continue advancing Chinese interests while maintaining a stable environment, which reflects a liaison between Confucianism and Legalism.

Nonetheless, official Chinese exceptionalism is appealing based on the history since 1979. The PRC has not been involved in any military conflicts since the Sino-Vietnamese War in 1979. Despite territorial disputes with several neighbours, the PRC has risen peacefully without conquering any countries. This is indeed a remarkable achievement for a major power, and Beijing can tout it to legitimate Chinese exceptionalism. As pointed out before, no one can predict with certainty if China will continue to rise peacefully given the intensifying geopolitical climate.

VII. CONCLUSION

This article has explored the complex landscape of Chinese exceptionalism, tracing its evolution from imperial assertions of central supremacy to contemporary manifestations as a “civilisational state.” The journey through historical, cultural, and political dimensions has unveiled a nuanced picture of how China perceives itself and projects its identity onto the global stage.

A critical insight from this analysis is the dualistic nature of Chinese exceptionalism, which seeks to uphold a peaceful, harmonious world vision while also preparing for strategic dominance. The discourse surrounding China’s rise, particularly regarding “benevolent pacifism” and “harmonious inclusionism,” contrasts sharply with the realpolitik strategies underpinning its regional and global actions. This juxtaposition reflects a broader struggle within international relations where historical narratives and geopolitical realities often clash.

The exploration of "Sino-speak," mainly through the works of Martin Jacques and Zhang Weiwei, underscores the reimagining of China's role on the world stage. The "civilisational state" notion challenges the Westphalian international system, proposing a model where cultural legacy and moral philosophy drive political engagement rather than the mere pursuit of national interest. However, as this article argues, such narratives must be critically assessed against actual policy decisions and historical actions, which sometimes contradict the idealistic frameworks proposed by "civilisational" rhetoric.

Moreover, the discourse of Chinese exceptionalism, while rich in cultural and historical assertions, often overlooks the pragmatic and sometimes harsh realities of governance and international relations, as highlighted by the discussion on Legalism. The integration of Legalism into the conversation on Chinese exceptionalism provides a more grounded understanding of China's approach to power and control, suggesting that its pacifist and harmonious outward expressions may sometimes serve more as strategic facades than reflections of underlying policy intentions.

Exceptionalism should be developed based on real exceptions. Chinese civilisation is arguably the longest continuous ancient civilisation. It is presumably the only secular example among the major civilisations worldwide. Chinese civilisation also emphasises great unity (大一统 *dayitong*) since 221 BC when Qin unified China. By contrast, Europe has never truly unified into a single polity since the fall of the Roman Empire. Nonetheless, it is unrealistic to frame any hegemon as benign. A hegemon inevitably appears coercive to others, though the hegemon itself does not necessarily realise it.

Employing exceptionalist discourse to highlight differences or superiority compared to other countries may prove detrimental. In the short term, it can promote national glory. However, in the long term, it drives nationalism and chauvinism, which may force the state to be more assertive and aggressive, leading to irrational decisions in its foreign policy.

Finally, this article calls for more future research on Chinese exceptionalism. This research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of Chinese exceptionalism and aids in predicting potential shifts in global dynamics as China continues to rise as a significant world power. Future research needs to delve deeper into whether Confucianism is simply a gloss to cover Chinese Legalism-style foreign policy. It is equally important to consider how Chinese exceptionalism restrains China from engaging in *realpolitik* actions. Additionally, future studies can examine how other philosophies, such as Daoism and Moism, influence Imperial China and the PRC in domestic governance and foreign policy.

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